

HIPPOCAMPAL PHYSIOLOGY

Kodirov Abdugofur

Andijan State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6657596>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

hippocampus; memory; schizophrenia; parietal; superior temporal sulcus; social cognition

ABSTRACT

Memory impairment is a consistent feature of the schizophrenic syndrome. Hippocampal dysfunction has also been consistently demonstrated. This review will discuss neurophysiological and neuroanatomical aspects of memory formation and how they relate to memory impairment in schizophrenia. An understanding of the cellular physiology and connectivity of the hippocampus with other regions can also aid in understanding the relationship between schizophrenic declarative or relational memory deficits, working memory deficits and the clinical symptoms of the syndrome.

Declarative memory and working memory deficits have been consistently demonstrated to be associated with the schizophrenic syndrome [1,2]. Although individuals with hippocampal damage can rehearse information across small time intervals and retain it, under normal circumstances, the hippocampus is used to process and integrate information across very brief time intervals; and is active and used during working memory tasks [3–6]. In fact, many of the hippocampal-dependent memory tasks used with animals in conjunction with hippocampal single neuronal recordings and lesion studies could be classified as working memory tasks (e.g., T-maze, radial arm maze, etc.; reviewed in a later section). Schizophrenia is most likely a disorder involving aberrant activation. For this reason, it is important to understand that the role of the hippocampus in

memory depends on its functional and structural connection with cortex and, especially, with higher order perceptual areas, where memory is eventually stored. An understanding of the flow of activation and the nature of hippocampal function can illuminate the relationship between perception, misperception (hallucinations and delusions), memory and working memory. In this review, I will discuss the neural basis of declarative, relational and working memory. Evidence for the numerous types of hippocampal abnormality found in schizophrenia will be described [7]. Research will be summarized to show how the cellular physiology, connectivity and neuroanatomy of the hippocampal system may relate to the memory impairment seen in schizophrenia. The review will also present a framework for understanding how the properties of the hippocampal

system may relate to other aspects of the schizophrenic syndrome, such as the age of onset and other symptoms of the syndrome [8]. This framework provides for an understanding of the relationship between declarative or relational memory deficits, working memory deficits and other aspects of the schizophrenic syndrome, such as the age of onset and positive and negative symptoms (hallucinations, delusions, attention deficits, flat affect, etc.).

2. Review—Memory, the Hippocampus and Schizophrenia

Learning and memory are profoundly impaired in schizophrenia, and the impairment is stable over time. A review of 110 studies reported that 101 of those studies found evidence of an impairment in verbal declarative memory [1]. The memory impairment in schizophrenia was found to be selective when compared to other functions, such as abstraction, verbal fluency and motor function [9]. Memory impairments were also shown to be stable and not affected by moderating factors, such as the duration or severity of illness [10]. The hippocampus and related structures are essential for the declarative or relational memory function—the type of memory also affected in schizophrenia [6,11]. Correspondingly, abnormalities of the hippocampal system are the most consistently documented morphometric findings in schizophrenia [12,13]. Hippocampal volume reductions have also been confirmed using large numbers of subjects [14] and are convergent with numerous findings of abnormal neuropathology [15]. Hippocampal alterations in functional activity have also been consistently identified in schizophrenia; these will be discussed in more detail below [16].

2.1. Hippocampal Function, Anatomy and

Physiology as It Relates to Schizophrenia

The role of the hippocampus in relational (declarative) memory is in binding together multiple inputs to create and allow for the storage of representations of the associations among the constituent elements of scenes and events [17]. This function ultimately results in the storage of long-term memory in widespread cortical regions. The hippocampus communicates with widespread regions of cortex through a group of highly interconnected brain regions in the medial temporal lobe (these regions will be collectively referred to as the hippocampal system). Hence, aberrant activation of the hippocampus would affect perceptual cortical regions; especially those showing high functional connectivity with the hippocampal system. The hippocampal system consists of the dentate gyrus, cornu ammonis (CA) fields and the subiculum. The dentate gyrus is an input region, which receives input from the entorhinal cortex. The cornu ammonis (CA) fields of the hippocampus consist of pyramidal cells and are usually subdivided into four regions (CA1–CA4). The area that is often referred to as the parahippocampal gyrus in humans actually consists of several subregions. The dorsal part of the parahippocampal gyrus (inferior to the hippocampal fissure), throughout its extent, is called the subiculum (see Figure 1) [18–20]. The entorhinal cortex provides the major input to the hippocampus and also receives output from the CA1 layer via the subiculum [21]. The entorhinal cortex provides input to the hippocampus through two pathways, one projecting to the dentate gyrus and CA3 fields and the other to CA1 and the subiculum. The subiculum then sends a major input back to the entorhinal cortex. The subiculum

undergoes an unusual and –striking|| increase in myelination during late adolescence; a time when individuals with schizophrenia typically experience the onset of the disease [22]. There is also an increase in hippocampal volume at this time in males, and schizophrenia is more prevalent in males [23].

The entorhinal cortex has its main reciprocal connections with the perirhinal and parahippocampal cortices. Hence, the hippocampus communicates with widespread cortical areas through the entorhinal, perirhinal and parahippocampal cortices [24–26]. The hippocampus also contains fiber pathways that run longitudinally throughout its extent (for a discussion, see [27]). This would allow for the excitation between disparate portions of the hippocampal formation. The entorhinal cortex extends from the amygdala (anteriorly) to approximately 10 mm posterior to the most anterior aspect of the hippocampal fissure. The posterior parahippocampal region can be subdivided into cytoarchitectonic areas, TH (medially) and TF (laterally) according to the nomenclature of von Economo, that extend approximately from the posterior border of the entorhinal cortex to the posterior end of the hippocampus. These regions have a very complex configuration in humans [28]. For this reason, the entorhinal cortex, perirhinal cortex and the TH/TF areas are usually designated as the parahippocampal gyrus and measured together as one region in human morphometric and neuroimaging investigations. Ischemia and other trauma, such as closed head injury or traumatic brain injury, can produce selective damage to the hippocampus, and this damage is sometimes limited to one or a few subfields

[29]. This fact has allowed for advances in understanding the function of the hippocampus. Ischemic damage to even a portion of the hippocampus is sufficient to produce anterograde amnesia for declarative memory and prevents the formation of new declarative or relational memories [30–32]. Retrograde memory is memory for information or events that were previously learned. The extent of retrograde memory impairment resulting from hippocampal damage may be dependent on how much of the hippocampal system is damaged. For example, an anterograde memory impairment was evident in patient R.B., who had damage limited to the CA1 layer of the hippocampus, but the impairment was limited to only one or two years [32]. In other words, R.B.'s memory for events up to two years prior to the brain damage were missing, but more remote memories were intact. Patients who had more extensive damage to the hippocampal formation, including all of the CA cell fields, the dentate gyrus and portions of the entorhinal cortex, showed both an anterograde amnesia and a temporally graded retrograde amnesia for 15 to 25 years [30,33]. These findings are important, because they show that the role of the hippocampus is to allow for the consolidation of memory in other cortical regions and that this process proceeds over a number of years. Hence, long-term memory is not actually stored in the hippocampus or, if it is, the hippocampal representation is not necessary for the retrieval of long-term memories after a period of several years. The conceptualization of memory and perception as separate is at odds with this formulation of hippocampal function.

Information flows from the cortex to the hippocampus and back out to cortex; this is how memories are formed. In other words, memories are formed via the interplay over

time between perceptual regions (including higher order association cortex) and the hippocampus.

References:

1. Cirillo, M.A.; Seidman, L.J. Verbal declarative memory dysfunction in schizophrenia: from clinical assessment to genetics and brain mechanisms. *Neuropsychol.*
2. Goldman-Rakic, P.S. Working memory dysfunction in schizophrenia. *J. Neuropsychiatry Clin. Neurosci.* 1994, 6, 348–357.
3. Warren, D.E.; Duff, M.C.; Jensen, U.; Tranel, D.; Cohen, N.J. Hiding in plain view: Lesions of the medial temporal lobe impair online representation. *Hippocampus* 2012, 22, 1577–1588.
4. Watanabe, T.; Niki, H. Hippocampal unit activity and delayed response in the monkey. *Brain Res.* 1985, 325, 241–254.
5. Hannula, D.E.; Tranel, D.; Cohen, N.J. The long and the short of it: Relational memory impairments in amnesia, Even at short lags. *J. Neurosci.* 2006, 26, 8352–8359.
6. Wible, C.G.; Shenton, M.E.; McCarley, R.W. Functional neuroanatomy of the limbic system and planum temporale. In *Brain Imaging in Clinical Psychiatry*; Krishnan, R.R., Doraiswamy, P.M., Eds.; Marcel Dekker: New York, NY, USA, 1997; pp. 63–101.
7. Small, S.A.; Schobel, S.A.; Buxton, R.B.; Witter, M.P.; Barnes, C.A. A pathophysiological framework of hippocampal dysfunction in ageing and disease. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* 2011, 12, 585–601.